

LEVEL OF LEADERSHIP SKILLS AND INFLUENCING FACTORS AMONG AREA COORDINATORS IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE OF BATAAN: BASIS FOR A TARGETED PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This research evaluated the area coordinators' leadership skills and influencing factors in the Schools Division Office of Bataan. Using a descriptive research design, this study gathered data through an adopted research instrument that focused on the four indicators for leadership skills, such as communication, mentoring, technical assistance, and management styles. The findings served as the basis for proposing a targeted professional development program. To analyze the data, the weighted mean and standard deviation were used to determine the level of leadership skills, while inferential statistics tested for significant differences across profiles like age, sex, educational attainment, and years of experience. Findings revealed that a high level of leadership skills was demonstrated by the area coordinators, reflecting their effectiveness in the different instructional processes and assisting teachers. Moreover, the results also show that there is no significant difference in the profile of the respondents and their leadership skills, indicating that regardless of the demographic and professional background of the respondents, area coordinators' effectiveness remains consistent. To further maintain and build the area coordinators' leadership skills, a targeted professional development program was crafted.

Keywords: *leadership skills, communication, mentoring, technical assistance, management styles, targeted professional development.*

INTRODUCTION

The evolving landscape of 21st-century education demands a leadership paradigm that is deeply instructional, context-responsive, and collaborative. In contemporary educational systems, leadership is viewed as a distributed and shared function rather than just the school head's responsibility. The study of Ling et al. (2023) emphasizes that effective leadership includes different actors such as supervisors, coordinators, and instructional leaders who influence the organizational performance and teaching quality. Different models, such as distributed and instructional leadership, have been shown to improve accountability, collaboration, and effectiveness in schools, specifically in decentralized and complex education systems.

According to Lin (2022), there is a gap in studies focusing on the educational leaders at the mid-level, such as area or cluster coordinators, despite the growing research about leadership in schools. Additionally, most international and local studies continue to focus or concentrate on the principals or school heads, leaving the skills of the coordinators unassessed. Considering that area coordinators often serve as the link between teachers and offices, the limited attention given to their skills creates a gap that needs to be filled.

The Area Coordinators are entrusted with and designated to different responsibilities in the Schools Division Office of Bataan, including program implementation, monitoring, and providing technical assistance to schools. Their leadership skills greatly affect the educational programs and school support services. Mendoza and Calo (2024) reveal that professional growth, teacher performance, and overall school effectiveness were significantly influenced by strong leadership skills. Moreover, leadership that is aligned with the initiatives of professional development results in stronger instructional outcomes and organizational performance. The findings confirm that assessing the leadership skills of area coordinators is an important step to take in creating or planning any professional development interventions. With that, a mismatch in training programs will be avoided because it may lead to failure in addressing the issue in the skills.

This study aims to guide the design of a context-specific training that is aligned with the skills needed among leaders. The school head, teachers, and coordinators are some of the beneficiaries of the study. According to Abrea (2019), area coordinators are academic leaders who are responsible for overseeing a subject-specific program and mentoring teachers in school. They are essential; however, their leadership skills are sometimes overshadowed by different administrative workload and a lack of support from the organization. Area coordinators might have impacted the students' performance; however, some limitations might affect their ability.

This study is anchored on the researcher's professional conviction that educational leadership must be strengthened at all organizational levels to ensure quality and sustainability in education. Through the researcher's direct exposure to coordination and supervisory functions, the researcher has observed the varying leadership practices of area coordinators and their significant impact on school operations. This professional experience, coupled with the goals of the Doctor of Education program to enhance

leadership and management competencies, served as the primary motivation for undertaking this study. The need to establish empirical evidence and develop a responsive, targeted professional development program for area coordinators directly leads to the formulation of the research problems of this investigation.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the Level of Leadership Skills among Area Coordinators in the Schools Division Office of Bataan for the School Year 2025-2026.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4 number of years in teaching;
 - 1.5 number of years as area coordinator; and
 - 1.6 relevant trainings attended?
2. What is the level of leadership skills of the area coordinators in terms of:
 - 2.1 communication;
 - 2.2 mentoring;
 - 2.3 technical assistance; and
 - 2.4 management styles?
3. How may the factors affecting the area coordinators' leadership skills be described in terms of:
 - 3.1 organizational support;
 - 3.2 professional development opportunities;
 - 3.3 work environment;
 - 3.4 personal motivation; and
 - 3.5 availability of resources?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of leadership skills of the area coordinators when grouped according to their profiles?
5. Based on the results of the study, what targeted professional development program can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

The study aimed to determine the level of leadership skills of Area Coordinators in the Schools Division Office of Bataan. Descriptive research, focusing on leadership skills, was employed in the study. This study was more interested in what happened than how or why. The respondents of the study were the teachers and the Area Coordinators in the Schools Division Office of Bataan for School Year 2025-2026. The study used convenience sampling to gather the data needed for the study.

As the research tool to collect data for the study, the researcher adopted a research questionnaire from Pagarigan and Guanzon (2025) on their study entitled “Area Coordinators’ Leadership Skills and Teachers’ Performance”. The data gathered from the respondents were encoded, tabulated, and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools aligned with the specific problems of the study. To describe the profile of the teachers and area coordinators in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, number of years in teaching, and relevant trainings attended, frequency counts and percentage distribution were employed. The level of leadership skills of area coordinators across indicators such as communication, mentoring, technical assistance, and management styles, as well as the factors affecting the leadership skills, was assessed using weighted mean and standard deviation.

To test the hypothesis of the study, non-parametric inferential statistics were utilized due to the ordinal nature of the Likert-scale data. Specifically, the Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine whether there is a significant difference in the level of leadership skills when area coordinators are grouped according to sex. Furthermore, the Kruskal-Wallis H test was applied to check the significant differences in leadership skills when coordinators are grouped according to their highest educational attainment and number of years in teaching. All inferential tests were set at a 0.05 level of significance to determine whether to reject or fail to reject the null hypothesis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part I displays the profile of the teachers in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, number of years in teaching, number of years as area coordinator, and relevant training attended.

Part II shows the area coordinators’ level of leadership skills in terms of organizational support, mentoring, technical assistance, and management styles.

Part III displays the profile of the area coordinators in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, number of years in teaching, number of years as area coordinator, and relevant training attended.

Part IV reveals the factors affecting the leadership skills among area coordinators in terms of organizational support, professional development opportunities, work environment, personal motivation, and availability of resources.

Part V reveals the relationship between the level of leadership skills and the respondents’ profiles.

Part VI presents the targeted professional development program.

Part I displays the profile of the teacher respondents in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, number of years in teaching, number of years as area coordinator, and relevant training attended.

Table 1. The profile of the teachers in terms of age

Age	Frequency	Percent
22 years old	1	1.35
23 years old	2	2.70
24 years old	4	5.41
25 years old	1	1.35
26 years old	4	5.41
27 years old	6	8.11
28 years old	3	4.05
29 years old	4	5.41
30 years old	3	4.05
31 years old	4	5.41
32 years old	4	5.41
33 years old	5	6.76
34 years old	4	5.41
35 years old	3	4.05
36 years old	5	6.76
37 years old	2	2.70
38 years old	3	4.05
39 years old	3	4.05
40 years old	3	4.05
41 years old	3	4.05
43 years old	1	1.35
44 years old	1	1.35
45 years old	2	2.70
49 years old	2	2.70
51 years old	1	1.35
Total	74	100

Table 1 shows the respondents' age profile, indicating a wide age distribution among teachers who rated the area coordinators, with the highest frequency at 27 years old, or 8.11%, followed by 33 and 36 years old or 6.76%. Most age groups fall within the mid-20s to late-30s, indicating that the teaching workforce is relatively young to middle-aged. Very few respondents are in the older brackets or above 40, each contributing only 1.35% to 4.05%. Overall, the sample reflects a heterogeneous age distribution.

The results indicate that the teaching workforce is predominantly composed of young to middle-aged individuals, particularly those in their mid-20s to late-30s. This suggests a dynamic and energetic group that is likely open to innovation and new teaching strategies. At the same time, the presence of older teachers, although limited, contributes valuable experience and stability within the school environment. The wide distribution of ages reflects diversity in perspectives, which can enhance collaboration and problem-solving. Younger teachers may bring technological adaptability, while older teachers provide mentorship and guidance. This balance creates opportunities for professional learning across age groups. However, the relatively low number of senior teachers may indicate a need for stronger mentoring structures. It also implies potential challenges in institutional memory retention.

The findings are supported by OECD (2021), which reported that a balanced age distribution among teachers fosters both innovation and stability in educational settings. Younger teachers are often more open to new pedagogical approaches, while experienced teachers contribute institutional knowledge and mentorship. This combination enhances overall school effectiveness and teacher collaboration. Moreover, age diversity has been linked to improved problem-solving and decision-making within an organization.

Table 2. The profile of the teachers in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	33	44.59
Female	41	55.41
Total	74	100

Table 2 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. This table presents the number of teachers who evaluated the level of leadership skills among area coordinators in the Schools Division Office of Bataan. It can be gleaned that the majority of the respondents are female, which is 41 or 55.41%, while the male respondents are 33 or 44.59%.

The findings show a slight predominance of female teachers, which reflects a common trend in the education sector. Despite this, the distribution remains relatively balanced, indicating representation from both sexes. This balance suggests that teaching effectiveness is not dependent on gender but on skills and competence. The presence of both male and female teachers contributes to diverse teaching styles and classroom management approaches. It also provides students with varied role models, which can positively influence their development. Gender diversity promotes inclusivity and mutual respect within the workplace. Furthermore, it enhances collaboration among educators. The results also imply that leadership perceptions are not biased toward a particular sector. Overall, the data support gender equality in the teaching profession.

According to UNESCO (2022), gender diversity in education contributes to an inclusive learning environment and improved teaching outcomes. The presence of both male and female educators enhances student engagement and provides varied role models. Furthermore, balanced gender representation supports equity and fairness in institutional practices. This diversity is essential for fostering a well-rounded educational experience.

Table 3. The profile of the teachers in terms of the highest educational attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	25	33.78
MAED Units	20	27.03
CAR for Master's Degree	12	16.22
Master's Degree	13	17.57
Doctoral Units	4	5.41
Total	74	100

Table 3 depicts the profile of the teachers in terms of their highest educational attainment. Based on the table, the majority of teachers hold a Bachelor's Degree, which comprises 25 individuals or 33.78%, followed by those with MAED Units with 20 individuals or 27.03% and Master's Degree with 13 individuals or 17.57%. Only a small proportion have reached Doctoral units studies with only 4 individuals or 5.41%. This indicates that most teachers are still in the process of advancing their academic qualifications. The distribution reflects a developing professional profile in terms of higher education.

The results reveal that most teachers are still in the process of advancing their academic qualifications. This indicates a strong commitment to professional growth and lifelong learning. The presence of teachers with ongoing graduate studies suggests a proactive approach to improving teaching competencies. However, the relatively small number of those with doctoral qualifications highlights a gap in advanced specialization. This may affect the depth of research-based teaching practices in the institution. Nonetheless, continuous academic pursuit reflects a positive trend toward professional development. It also suggests that teachers are motivated to enhance their instructional effectiveness. Encouraging higher-level education could further improve teaching quality.

The relatively low percentage of teachers with Master's or Doctoral-level preparation suggests potential gaps in access to or engagement with postgraduate learning opportunities. Akhtar (2024) further argues that without structured support for further education, improvements in teaching practices may remain limited. Therefore, investing in pathways for teachers to advance their qualifications could directly enhance both classroom instruction and the overall leadership support they receive from coordinators. These findings align with the broader need for systematic professional development to sustain educational quality.

Table 4. The profile of the teachers in terms of the number of years in teaching

Number of Years in Teaching	Frequency	Percent
0.5	1	1.35
1	5	6.76
2	3	4.05
3	4	5.41
3.75	2	2.70
4	6	8.11
5	6	8.11
6	3	4.05
7	4	5.41
8	8	10.81
9	5	6.76
10	3	4.05
11	5	6.76
12	4	5.41
13	5	6.76
14	5	6.76
15	3	4.05
20	1	1.35
23	1	1.35
Total	74	100

Table 4 shows the profile of the teachers in terms of the number of years in teaching. The highest percentage is observed at 8 years, with 8 individuals or 10.81%, followed by 4 and 5 years with a total of 6 respondents or 8.11%. Most teachers fall within 1-14 years of experience. Additionally, the sample shows diversity in teaching tenure. Overall, the respondents represent a balanced range of teaching experience.

The findings indicate that most teachers fall within the early to mid-career stage, particularly between 1 and 14 years of experience. This suggests that they have already developed foundational teaching skills while still being open to learning and improvement. The diversity in teaching experience allows for a mix of fresh ideas and practical expertise. Mid-career teachers are likely to be more confident and adaptable in their instructional practices. However, the limited number of highly experienced teachers may indicate a need for a stronger mentorship system. Experience contributes to competence, but it must be supported by continuous professional development. The distribution also reflects a balanced teaching workforce. It also implies that teachers are still in the process of refining their skills.

Part II shows the area coordinators' level of leadership skills in terms of organizational support, mentoring, technical assistance, and management styles.

Table 5. The level of leadership skills of the area coordinators in terms of communication

Communication My area coordinator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Ensures team members understand their roles by providing clear instructions and achievable goals.	3.14	0.80	Often
2. Actively listens to teachers' ideas, concerns, and suggestions.	3.07	0.85	Often
3. Creates an open, collaborative environment with respectful participation.	3.08	0.72	Often
4. Manages communication effectively to keep the team informed.	3.09	0.83	Often
5. Clearly explains school policies to minimize misunderstandings.	3.00	0.88	Often
6. Handles challenges calmly and objectively.	2.96	0.90	Often
7. Identifies issues proactively to implement effective resolutions.	2.96	0.82	Often
8. Applies critical thinking and data analysis to uncover causes of conflicts.	3.09	0.74	Often
9. Develops practical, creative solutions by involving team members.	2.93	0.93	Often
10. Resolves problems promptly.	2.96	0.87	Often
General Mean and SD	3.03	0.83	Often

Table 5 shows the level of leadership skills among area coordinators in terms of communication. The general mean of 3.03 with a standard deviation of 0.83 is interpreted as "Often," indicating that the communication skills of coordination are in "high level". All indicators fall within the same interpretation, showing uniform responses across items. The highest mean is 3.14, suggesting clarity in instructions is a strong area. The lowest mean from 2.93 to 2.96 indicates slight variability in problem-solving aspects. The standard deviation values around 0.80 to 0.90 suggest moderate, generally

consistent. The data indicate positive but not very high communication performance. Overall, coordinators demonstrate effective communication practices

This indicates that coordinators are capable of conveying information clearly and maintaining collaboration among teachers. Strengths are evident in providing clear instructions and fostering a respectful environment. However, slightly lower scores in problem-solving communication suggest areas for improvement. This implies that while communication is effective, it may not always be strategic in addressing complex issues. The consistency in responses reflects shared perceptions among teachers. Effective communication contributes to a positive organizational climate. It also enhances teamwork and coordination.

Edoloverio et al. (2024) found that educational leadership research remains disproportionately focused on Western contexts, and they advocate for a more inclusive knowledge base that authentically reflects diverse socio-cultural settings. Their study emphasizes that incorporating insights from non-Western scholarship enriches academic discourse and enhances the relevance of leadership practices across different educational systems. Thus, the communication skills observed in this study contribute to the growing body of non-Western leadership evidence, showing that coordinators in this context exhibit positive communication behaviors that align with global leadership expectations while being situated within a local Philippine educational setting.

Table 6. The level of leadership skills of the area coordinators in terms of mentoring

Mentoring As an area coordinator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Identifies teachers' growth areas and provides tailored advice for improvement.	3.12	0.68	Often
2. Helps teachers set realistic goals and tracks progress.	3.03	0.84	Often
3. Recommends workshops to promote lifelong learning and skills development.	2.88	0.79	Often
4. Observes classrooms and suggests innovative strategies to improve instruction.	3.00	0.86	Often
5. Provides timely, constructive feedback.	2.93	0.82	Often
6. Facilitates collaborative activities to encourage shared learning.	2.91	0.81	Often
7. Monitors teachers' progress through performance reviews and follow-ups.	2.82	0.87	Often
8. Introduces innovative teaching methods.	2.85	0.82	Often

9. Ensures teachers have access to professional development tools and materials.	2.91	0.72	Often
10. Creates an atmosphere of encouragement and trust.	3.01	0.82	Often
General Mean and SD	2.95	0.80	Often

Table 6 presents the level of leadership skills among area coordinators in terms of mentoring having a general mean of 2.95 with standard deviation of 0.80, indicating that mentoring is “Often” practiced or “high level”. Most items fall close to the mean, showing consistency in mentoring practices. The highest mean of 3.12 reflects the strength in identifying teachers’ needs. The lowest mean of 2.82 suggests room for improvement in monitoring progress. This suggests agreement among respondents. Further, mentoring is present but not at a highly advanced level. Overall, coordinators exhibit moderate mentoring effectiveness.

The findings indicate that mentoring is moderately practiced among coordinators. This suggests that teachers receive guidance, but mentoring strategies may not be fully maximized. Strengths are seen in identifying teachers’ needs and providing support for improvement. However, weaker areas, such as monitoring progress, highlight gaps in sustained mentoring. This may limit the long-term impact of mentoring programs. Consistency in responses suggests general agreement among teachers about mentoring practices. Effective mentoring is essential for professional growth and instructional improvement. The results imply a need for more structured mentoring systems. Strengthening mentoring could enhance teacher performance.

Hobson (2021) examined the concept of “judgementoring,” which refers to a harmful form of mentoring where mentors are overly judgemental and evaluative rather than supportive. The study found that judgementoring can negatively affect teachers’ professional learning, development, and well-being. Hobson advocated for bringing mentoring “onside” by shifting toward more constructive, supportive mentoring approaches that prioritize teacher growth and psychological safety. The findings highlight that effective mentoring should avoid excessive judgment and instead focus on fostering trust, collaboration, and ongoing professional development. Thus, the study underscores the importance of mentoring practices that enhance rather than undermine teacher outcomes.

Table 7. The level of leadership skills of the area coordinators in terms of technical assistance

Technical Assistance As an area coordinator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Provides high-quality instructional materials aligned with the curriculum.	3.03	0.81	Often

2. Guides teachers in using innovative teaching tools and strategies.	2.96	0.80	Often
3. Assists teachers in integrating digital platforms and technology.	2.91	0.74	Often
4. Collaborates in developing well-structured curricula.	2.84	0.83	Often
5. Helps align instructional methods with student learning needs.	2.93	0.80	Often
6. Provides technical support for classroom management.	3.01	0.87	Often
7. Streamlines access to essential resources.	2.99	0.79	Often
8. Organizes professional development activities.	3.01	0.73	Often
9. Provides follow-up support during implementation of strategies.	2.93	0.83	Often
10. Provides technical assistance as needed.	2.96	0.85	Often
General Mean and SD	2.96	0.81	Often

Table 7 presents the level of leadership skills among area coordinators in terms of technical assistance, with a general mean of 2.96 and a standard deviation of 0.81 shows that technical assistance is “Often” provided or “high level”. All indicators are consistently interpreted, indicating stable support practices. The highest mean of 3.03 reflects strong provision of materials. Lower means around 2.84 to 2.91 suggest improvement is needed in curriculum collaboration. This implies differing experiences among teachers. Further, technical support is adequate but not highly optimized. Overall, coordinators provide consistent but improvable technical assistance.

The results show that technical assistance is consistently provided but not at an advanced level. Coordinators appear to support teacher with instructional materials and basic guidance. However, lower ratings in curriculum collaboration and technology integration suggest areas for improvement. This indicates that support may not fully meet modern educational demands. Variability in responses reflects differences in teachers’ experiences with technical support. Effective technical assistance is essential for improving teaching quality. It also supports innovation in instructional practices. Enhancing digital literacy and resource availability is necessary.

Moreover, Shah (2022) found that teachers’ well-equipped preparation with ICT tools and facilities is one of the main factors in the success of technology-based teaching and learning. The study also revealed that professional development training programs for teachers played a key role in enhancing students’ learning quality. In the context of technical assistance, these findings suggest that effective technical support for teachers should include both (1) ensuring adequate access to ICT resources (hardware, software, digital tools) and (2) providing ongoing training and professional development to help

teachers integrate technology effectively into their instruction. Without these forms of technical assistance, teachers may struggle to replace traditional teaching methods with technology-based approaches, limiting the overall effectiveness of ICT integration in schools.

Table 8. The level of leadership skills of the area coordinators in terms of management styles

Management Styles As an area coordinator	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Adapts leadership approaches for effective direction.	2.97	0.95	Often
2. Fosters teamwork through open communication.	3.01	0.84	Often
3. Recognizes individual strengths and fosters inclusivity.	2.95	0.90	Often
4. Addresses disagreements promptly.	2.97	0.84	Often
5. Adjusts strategies to meet unexpected challenges.	2.88	0.86	Often
6. Fosters a positive, motivating environment.	3.03	0.81	Often
7. Makes confident and timely decisions.	2.89	0.84	Often
8. Sets clear expectations and follows up on commitments.	2.91	0.72	Often
9. Builds trust through integrity and reliability.	3.09	0.74	Often
10. Seeks constructive feedback to improve leadership.	2.96	0.88	Often
General Mean and SD	2.97	0.84	Often

Table 8 depicts the area coordinators' level of leadership skills in terms of management styles with a general mean of 2.97 and a standard deviation of 0.84 is interpreted as "Often," indicating effective Management practices or "high level". The highest mean of 3.09 shows strength in building trust. Moreover, management practices are generally positive but not highly differentiated. Overall, coordinators demonstrate consistent management styles.

The findings indicate that coordinators demonstrate generally effective management practices. Strengths are evident in building trust and fostering a positive environment. However, adaptability and decision-making appear to be weaker areas. This suggests that coordinators may perform well in stable situations but face challenges in dynamic contexts. The consistency of responses reflects shared perceptions among teachers. Effective management requires flexibility and responsiveness to change. Improving

decision-making skills could enhance leadership effectiveness. The results also highlight the importance of continuous feedback. Finally, management styles are stable but not fully optimized.

Part III displays the profile of the area coordinators in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, number of years in teaching, number of years as area coordinator, and relevant training attended.

Table 9. The profile of the coordinators in terms of age

Age	Frequency	Percent
23 years old	2	3.70
25 years old	1	1.85
26 years old	1	1.85
27 years old	4	7.41
28 years old	4	7.41
29 years old	2	3.70
30 years old	3	5.56
31 years old	4	7.41
32 years old	3	5.56
33 years old	5	9.26
34 years old	6	11.11
35 years old	1	1.85
36 years old	3	5.56
37 years old	3	5.56
40 years old	1	1.85
41 years old	1	1.85
43 years old	4	7.41
45 years old	1	1.85
46 years old	2	3.70
49 years old	2	3.70
52 years old	1	1.85
Total	54	100

Table 9 presents the age distribution of the coordinators, showing a diverse range of ages among the 54 respondents. The highest frequency is observed at 34 years old or 11.11%, followed by 33 years old or 9.26%, while several age groups, such as 27, 28, 31, and 43 years old, each account for 7.41%. The data indicate that most coordinators fall within the late 20s to mid- 30s age bracket, suggesting a relatively young to middle-aged leadership group. Only a small proportion belong to the older age groups above 40, each contributing

minimal percentages, indicating a mix of early-career and experienced coordinators, which may contribute to varied perspectives in leadership practices.

This suggests a leadership group that is energetic, adaptable, and open to innovation. The presence of some older coordinators adds experience and maturity to leadership practices. The diversity in age allows for a balance of new ideas and established strategies. Younger leaders may be more flexible, while older ones provide guidance and stability. This combination enhances leadership effectiveness. However, the limited number of highly growth opportunities for emerging leaders.

Table 10. The profile of the coordinators in terms of sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	25	46.30
Female	29	53.70
Total	54	100

Table 10 shows the distribution of coordinators based on sex. Out of 54 respondents, 29 or 53.70% are female, while 25 or 46.30% are male. This indicates a slight predominance of female coordinators in the sample. However, the difference between the two groups is relatively small, suggesting a near-balanced representation of both sexes.

The findings reveal a nearly balanced distribution of male and female coordinators. This suggests that leadership roles are accessible to both sexes. The slight predominance of female coordinators reflects broader trends in education. However, the minimal difference indicates fairness and inclusivity in leadership opportunities. Gender balance promotes diverse perspectives in decision-making. IT also enhances collaboration within the organization. The results imply that leadership effectiveness is not influenced by sex. Instead, competence and skills are more important factors.

Table 11. The profile of the coordinators in terms of highest educational attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	6	11.11
MAED Units	6	11.11
CAR for Master's Degree	8	14.81
Master's Degree	14	25.93
Doctoral Units	18	33.33
CAR for Doctoral	2	3.70
Total	54	100

Table 11 presents the highest educational attainment of the coordinators. The largest proportion of respondents are those with doctoral degrees, with 18 individuals or 33.33%, followed by those with a Master's Degree with 14 individuals or 25.93%. Smaller proportions include CAR for Master's Degree with 8 individuals or 14.81%, and both Bachelor's Degree and MAED Units with 11.11% each or 6 individuals, while only 3.70% have CAR for doctoral level.

The data indicate that the majority of coordinators are engaged in advanced academic pursuits. With a significant number already in doctoral-level studies. This suggests a high level of professional and academic qualification, which may positively influence their leadership competence and decision-making abilities.

Table 12. The profile of the coordinators in terms of number of years in teaching

Number of Years in Teaching	Frequency	Percent
0.75	1	1.85
1	1	1.85
2	2	3.70
3	1	1.85
4	2	3.70
5	5	9.26
6	4	7.41
7	3	5.56
8	3	5.56
9	6	11.11
10	6	11.11
11	5	9.26
12	3	5.56
13	3	5.56
14	2	3.70
15	2	3.70
18	1	1.85
20	1	1.85
21	1	1.85
22	1	1.85
28	1	1.85
Total	54	100

Table 12 illustrates the distribution of coordinators according to their teaching experience. The highest frequencies are observed at 9 years and 10 years or 11.11% each, followed by 5 years and 11 years or 9.26% each. Most respondents fall within the 5 to 12 years range, indicating a concentration of mid-career professionals. Only a few respondents are

at the extremes, less than 2 years or more than 20 years, each representing 1.85% to 3.70%.

The data show a moderately varied but concentrated distribution, suggesting that most coordinators have accumulated sufficient teaching experience to support their leadership roles. This level of experience may contribute to more informed decision-making and effective management practices.

Table 13. The profile of the coordinators in terms of attended relevant trainings

Attended relevant trainings	Frequency	Percent
Yes	31	57.41
No	23	42.59
Total	54	100

Table 13 presents the distribution of coordinators based on their attendance in relevant trainings. Out of 54 respondents, 31 or 57.41% reported having attended relevant training. While 23 or 45.59% indicated otherwise.

This shows that a majority of coordinators have been exposed to professional training, which may contribute positively to their leadership competencies. However, the relatively high percentage of those who have not attended training suggests a gap in professional development opportunities, which may affect consistency in leadership effectiveness across coordinators.

Part IV reveals the factors affecting the leadership skills among area coordinators in terms of organizational support, professional development opportunities, work environment, personal motivation, and availability of resources.

Table 14. The factors affecting the area coordinators' leadership skills be described in terms of organizational support

Organizational Support	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The organization values my contributions to the institution.	3.13	0.83	Agree
2. The organization supports my professional growth and development.	3.11	0.90	Agree
3. Leadership provides clear guidance and direction in my role.	3.07	0.80	Agree
4. I receive timely and constructive feedback from supervisors.	2.83	0.80	Agree

5. My concerns and suggestions are taken seriously by management.	2.85	0.79	Agree
6. I feel recognized and appreciated for my work.	2.93	0.84	Agree
7. Communication from leadership fosters a supportive and inclusive climate.	3.17	0.75	Agree
8. Policies and procedures are clearly communicated and consistently implemented.	2.85	0.79	Agree
9. The organization provides assistance when I encounter work-related challenges.	3.04	0.70	Agree
10. I feel that the administration genuinely cares about my well-being.	3.06	0.81	Agree
General Mean and SD	3.00	0.80	Agree

Table 14 shows the factors affecting leadership skills in terms of organizational support, with a general mean of 3.00 and standard deviation of 0.80 interpreted as “Agree”. This indicates that coordinators generally perceive that the organization provides adequate support. Among the indicators, the highest mean of 3.17 suggests that communication from leadership fosters a supportive and inclusive climate, while the lowest mean of 2.83 indicates relatively less agreement on receiving timely and constructive feedback. Overall, organizational support is present but may still require strengthening, particularly in feedback mechanisms.

The findings indicate that coordinators generally perceive organizational support positively. This suggests that the institution provides guidance, recognition, and assistance. Strong communication from leadership is a notable strength. However, lower ratings in the feedback mechanism indicate areas for improvement. Effective support systems are essential for leadership development. They also enhance motivation and job satisfaction. The consistency of responses reflects shared perceptions among coordinators. Improving the feedback process could strengthen.

Table 15. The factors affecting the area coordinators’ leadership skills be described in terms of professional development opportunities

Professional Development Opportunities	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I am satisfied with the professional development opportunities available to me.	2.87	0.95	Agree
1. The training programs offered are relevant to my leadership responsibilities.	2.83	0.93	Agree
2. The organization encourages continuous learning and improvement.	3.06	0.94	Agree
3. Professional development activities enhance my leadership competencies.	3.07	0.80	Agree

4. Opportunities for mentorship or coaching are accessible.	2.96	0.82	Agree
5. I am given equal access to seminars, workshops, and conferences.	2.80	0.98	Agree
6. Professional development programs address current educational trends and needs.	3.15	0.74	Agree
7. I am encouraged to apply newly acquired skills in my workplace.	3.06	0.81	Agree
8. There are sufficient opportunities for career advancement.	3.04	0.82	Agree
9. Professional development initiatives contribute positively to my job performance.	3.19	0.73	Agree
General Mean and SD	3.00	0.85	Agree

Table 15 reflects the perception of coordinators regarding professional development opportunities, with a general mean of 3.00 and a standard deviation of 0.85, interpreted as Agree. This suggests that respondents' mean of 3.19 indicates that professional development contributes positively to job performance, while the lowest mean of 2.80 reflects concerns about equal access to seminars and training. The relatively higher standard deviation of 0.85 suggests greater variability in responses, indicating that experiences with professional development may differ among coordinators.

This implies that while opportunities exist, equity and accessibility remain areas for improvement. The results show that coordinators generally agree that professional development opportunities are available. This indicates that the organization supports continuous learning. However, concerns about equal access suggest inconsistencies. Some coordinators may have more opportunities than others. Professional development is essential for improving leadership skills. It also supports career growth and performance. Addressing accessibility issues is important for fairness. The findings highlight the need for more inclusive programs.

Table 16. The factors affecting the area coordinators' leadership skills be described in terms of work environment

Work Environment	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The work environment is pleasant and conducive to productivity.	3.19	0.65	Agree
2. I feel safe and secure in my workplace.	3.26	0.65	Agree
3. I receive regular constructive feedback from leadership.	2.89	0.72	Agree
4. Collaboration among colleagues is encouraged and practiced.	3.09	0.71	Agree

5. Communication channels within the organization are clear and effective.	3.06	0.68	Agree
6. The organizational culture promotes respect and professionalism.	2.98	0.81	Agree
7. Work responsibilities are fairly distributed among staff.	2.89	0.86	Agree
8. Conflicts are managed effectively and professionally.	2.89	0.72	Agree
9. Leadership fosters teamwork and cooperation.	3.20	0.68	Agree
10. The overall climate of the organization supports high performance.	3.13	0.73	Agree
General Mean and SD	3.06	0.72	Agree

Table 16 presents the work environment as a factor affecting leadership skills, yielding a general mean of 3.06 and standard deviation of 0.72, interpreted as Agree. This indicates that coordinators generally perceive their work environment as supportive. The highest mean of 3.26 reflects that respondents feel safe and secure in their workplace, while lower means of 2.89 suggest weaker perceptions regarding feedback, workload distribution, and conflict management.

The relatively low standard deviation indicates consistency in responses, suggesting a shared perception of the work environment. Overall, the findings imply that while the environment is generally conducive, specific organizational practices may still need enhancement.

Table 17. The factors affecting the area coordinators' leadership skills be described in terms of Personal Motivation

Personal Motivation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I feel motivated to achieve my professional goals.	3.46	0.54	Strongly Agree
1. I set personal development goals regularly.	3.56	0.50	Strongly Agree
2. I am willing to put in extra effort to perform my duties effectively.	3.59	0.50	Strongly Agree
3. I find my work meaningful and fulfilling.	3.39	0.53	Agree
4. I feel passionate about contributing to organizational success.	3.57	0.54	Strongly Agree

5. I remain committed even when faced with challenges.	3.74	0.48	Strongly Agree
6. I take initiative in improving my leadership skills.	3.59	0.53	Strongly Agree
7. I am confident in my ability to perform my responsibilities well.	3.63	0.56	Strongly Agree
8. I strive for excellence in my professional role.	3.80	0.41	Strongly Agree
9. I feel inspired to continuously improve my performance.	3.72	0.49	Strongly Agree
General Mean and SD	3.61	0.51	Strongly Agree

Table 17 shows that personal motivation has a general mean of 3.61 and a standard deviation of 0.51, interpreted as Strongly Agree. This indicates a high level of intrinsic motivation among coordinators. The highest mean of 3.80 suggests that respondents strive for excellence, while all indicators consistently fall within the “Agree” to “Strongly Agree” range.

This suggests that personal motivation is a significant strength and a key contributing factor to effective leadership. This indicates strong commitment and dedication to their roles. Highly motivated individuals are more likely to perform effectively. They also demonstrate initiative and resilience. Motivation drives continuous improvement and goal achievement. The consistency of responses reflects a shared sense of purpose. This major strength in leadership. It positively influences organizational performance.

Table 18. The factors affecting the area coordinators’ leadership skills be described in terms of availability of resources

Availability of Resources	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The necessary instructional materials are available when needed.	2.78	0.72	Agree
2. Technical resources (software, hardware, and tools) are adequate for my role.	2.76	0.55	Agree
3. There are sufficient financial resources to support programs and activities.	2.70	0.88	Agree
4. Human resources are sufficient to accomplish organizational objectives.	2.93	0.75	Agree
5. Facilities and equipment are properly maintained and functional.	2.87	0.65	Agree
6. I have access to updated reference materials and information.	3.02	0.63	Agree

7. Support services are available when technical or operational issues arise.	2.87	0.67	Agree
8. Resources are distributed fairly among personnel.	2.91	0.71	Agree
9. I can easily request additional resources when necessary.	2.70	0.74	Agree
10. The organization ensures that essential resources are provided in a timely manner.	2.94	0.74	Agree
General Mean and SD	2.85	0.70	Agree

Table 18 presents the availability of resources with a general mean of 2.85 and a standard deviation of 0.70, interpreted as Agree. This indicates that while resources are generally available, they may not be fully sufficient. The highest mean of 3.02 shows that access to updated reference materials is relatively adequate, whereas the lowest mean of 2.70 highlights concerns regarding financial resources and ease of requesting additional resources. Overall, this implies that resource availability is adequate but not optimal, potentially limiting leadership effectiveness.

This suggests that while basic needs are met, there are limitations. Issues such as financial resources and accessibility require attention. Unequal distribution of resources may affect performance. Adequate resources are essential for effective leadership. They support program implementation and innovation. The variability in responses reflects different experiences. Improving resource allocation is necessary.

Part V reveals the relationship between the level of leadership skills and the respondents' profiles.

Table 19. The difference in the level of leadership skills of the area coordinators when grouped according to sex

Sex		COMMUNICATION	MENTORING	TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE	MANAGEMENT STYLES	Decision	Remarks
Male	U	92.500	114.500	101.500	99.500	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.123	0.457	0.225	0.197		
Female	U	188.000	181.000	175.000	163.500	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.617	0.493	0.399	0.252		

Grouping Variable: Sex

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 19 examines differences in leadership skills based on sex. The result shows that all computed p-values ranging from 0.123 to 0.617 are greater than the 0.05 level of

significance, leading to the decision to fail to reject in leadership skills in terms of communication, mentoring, technical, and management styles when grouped according to sex. This implies that male and female coordinators demonstrate comparable levels of leadership skills, suggesting sex does not influence leadership effectiveness in this context

Table 20. The difference in the level of leadership skills of the area coordinators when grouped according to the highest educational attainment

Highest Educational Attainment		COMMUNICATION	MENTORING	TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE	MANAGEMENT STYLES	Decision	Remarks
Bachelor's Degree	H	2.627	4.683	5.976	6.572	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.622	0.321	0.201	0.160		
MAED Units	H	0.878	2.315	1.425	1.940	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.831	0.510	0.700	0.585		
CAR for Master's Degree	H	2.905	2.391	0.405	1.242	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.574	0.664	0.982	0.871		
Master's Degree	H	2.819	3.452	2.628	1.423	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.589	0.485	0.622	0.840		
Doctoral Units	H	2.400	0.600	0.600	1.500	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.121	0.439	0.439	0.221		

Grouping Variable: Highest Educational Attainment

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 20 presents the differences in leadership skills based on the highest educational attainment. All p-values ranging from 0.121 to 0.982 exceed the 0.05 significance level, resulting in the decision to fail to reject the null hypothesis across all indicators. This indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in leadership skills among coordinators when grouped according to educational attainment. Despite variations in educational levels, the results suggest that leadership skills are consistently demonstrated regardless of academic qualifications, implying that factors other than formal education may play a more critical role in leadership effectiveness.

Table 21. The difference in the level of leadership skills of the area coordinators when grouped according to Number of Years in Teaching

Number of Years in Teaching	COMMUNICATION	MENTORING	TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE	MANAGEMENT	Decision	Remarks
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1	H	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.406		
2	H	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368		
3	H	3.000	3.000	3.000	3.000	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.392	0.392	0.392	0.392		
3.7	H	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
5	p-value	0.317	0.317	0.317	0.317		
4	H	1.429	3.676	3.676	2.550	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.839	0.452	0.452	0.636		
5	H	3.571	3.051	3.144	1.932	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.312	0.384	0.370	0.587		
6	H	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368		
7	H	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368		
8	H	4.040	5.208	5.101	3.884	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.544	0.391	0.404	0.566		
9	H	3.526	3.526	3.800	4.000	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.317	0.317	0.284	0.261		
10	H	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.317	0.317	0.317	0.317		
11	H	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.406		
12	H	3.000	3.000	3.000	3.000	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.392	0.392	0.392	0.392		
13	H	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	p-value	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.406		
14	H	4.000	4.000	4.000	4.000		

	p-value	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.406	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho
	H	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000		
15	p-value	0.317	0.317	0.317	0.317	Not Significant	Fail to reject Ho

Grouping Variable: Number of Years in Teaching

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 21 presents the differences in leadership skills among area coordinators when grouped according to the number of years in teaching. All p-values are above 0.05, indicating no significant differences in leadership skills based on years of teaching. This results in failing to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that experience alone does not determine leadership effectiveness. The leadership skills are uniform across experience levels. This may imply that training support is a more influential factor. Overall, years of teaching do not significantly affect leadership skills.

Part VI presents the targeted professional development program.

The Targeted Professional Development Program is proposed for area coordinators aims to further build their leadership competencies, with a focus on communication, mentoring, technical assistance, and management styles. The program will start with leadership enhancement training held quarterly to boost coordinators' skills in instructional leadership, emotional intelligence, and strategic decision-making. This will be supported by annual technical assistance capacity-building sessions covering instructional coaching, curriculum alignment, ICT integration, and data-driven teaching strategies to better assist teachers in classrooms.

Additionally, a monthly mentoring and coaching program will be rolled out to build strong professional ties between area coordinators and teachers. To strengthen collaboration and shared leadership, professional learning communities (PLCs) will also be informed, allowing coordinators and teachers to discuss issues, exchange best practices, and work together on instructional challenges.

In addition, the program will set up a monitoring and evaluation system to track how effective all activities are. Quarterly assessments and feedback reports will be done to support ongoing improvement and data-informed decisions. Another major part of the program is strengthening resource and support systems to make sure area coordinators have enough materials, digital tools, and a supportive work environment. Finally, it promotes research and innovation by involving coordinators in action research and project development, allowing them to create evidence-based strategies that help improve educational practices over time.

Overall, this comprehensive professional development program seeks to maintain strong leadership performance while addressing growth areas, which will ultimately boost teacher productivity and improve learning outcomes.

Conclusions

The study found that area coordinators in the Schools Division Office of Bataan show a high level of leadership skills in communication, mentoring, technical assistance, and management styles, making them effective instructional leaders and supports for teachers. The results show they communicate effectively, stating expectations, building professional relationships, and helping teachers reach instructional goals

Leadership skills did not differ significantly across age, sex, educational attainment, or years of experience, suggesting that effectiveness depends more on ongoing training, organizational support, and resource access than on personal or professional background.

Overall, while coordinators display a high level of leadership skills, continuous and focused professional development is still needed, especially to improve technical assistance and collaborative practices. Moreover, a structured and targeted professional development program was proposed to strengthen the skills, standardize practices, and address gaps.

Recommendations

After taking into account the conclusions and findings, the study arrived at the following recommendations:

Area coordinators need advanced training on instructional coaching, curriculum integration, and educational technology to deliver technical assistance that is both consistent and aligned with current teaching methods.

Hold regular seminars, workshops, and mentoring sessions to maintain and grow leadership skills across all coordinators, since effectiveness is not tied to their demographic or professional background. Moreover, a system for continuous monitoring and evaluation should be established to assess the effectiveness of the implemented training program and ensure alignment with the needs of area coordinators.

Researchers may conduct similar or related studies utilizing the same methodologies but in a different Division.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher adhered to ethical standards throughout the study. The approval from the Dean of the Graduate School and the Schools Division Office of Bataan was secured before the data collection took place. Moreover, informed consent was obtained from the teachers and area coordinators after the discussion of the purpose, procedure, and respondents' rights in the study, with the option that, without any consequences, respondents can withdraw at any time. No identifying information was revealed or disclosed in any part of the study, and confidentiality and anonymity were upheld strictly.

All data collected complied with the Data Privacy Act, making sure that the information was securely stored and used for academic purposes only. The respondents' well-being was protected, ensuring that they experienced no pressure, harm, or discomfort. Academic integrity was maintained by properly citing all sources and by avoiding plagiarism. In the conduct of the study, the researcher confirms that there is no conflict of interest, and findings were objectively interpreted, without manipulation or bias, and the results were applied and used strictly for research and educational use.

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